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VIOLA: Detecting VIOLATIONS of Behaviors from Streams of Sensor Data

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Evaluation of VIOLA using a real dataset

This appendix contains additional material for the paper VIOLA: Detecting VIOLATIONS of Behaviors from Streams of Sensor Data. VIOLA automatically mines an Extended-GSM (E-GSM) model from a labeled sensor log. The process model represents activity labels as *stages*, i.e. the abstraction of the raw sensor data, while conditions on the sensors predicate on *data flow guards* and *milestones*. The streaming conformance checking is able to process a stream of sensors, represent it in form of an abstracted process model, and verify at run-time if new instances of the process are compliant.

To evaluate the VIOLA approach, two experiments are conducted, one based on synthetic event logs, and the other based on a real dataset. The experiment based on synthetic data is extensively explained in the paper, while the experiment conducted using a real dataset is explained in this appendix. The objective of this experiment is to assess the real applicability of the approach, both in terms of identification of activities/deviations and timing.

The dataset used in the experiment is the Kasteren dataset [1] which describes the movement of a person in a smart environment equipped with sensors, in form of sensor measurements. The sensor log consists of 28 days of recording, where each day is associated with a case identifier and a total of 1068 events. The log contains events from 14 sensors, and 7 different activities are identified, and labeled.

For the processing of the dataset, the same approach followed for the experiments on the synthetic logs is adopted. A crucial observation is that there is no knowledge about the executed behaviors. Therefore, by dividing the dataset into train and test sets, we cannot guarantee that the behaviors in the test set actually conform to the modeled ones. Given these assumptions, we proceed with the pre-processing of the log. To split the log into time windows we compute the mean duration of each activity identifier, and select the window size accordingly. Hence, the sensor log is split into windows of 2 minutes, and the train set is used for the derivation of both Directly-Follows Graph (DFG) and rules. In the online setting, the test set is processed by simulating a stream.

The test set contains 56 activities, of which 49 were correctly recognized during the streaming phase. However, 20 false positives were also identified.

Fig. 1: Time required to process each activity (i.e., as a collection of individual events) of the real dataset expressed in milliseconds. Avg and max times are reported as well.

The reason is that the set of sensors associated with a specific activity is not discriminatory: many sensors are shared by multiple activities, leading to a misclassification of the activity label. Despite that, to a large extent, the approach was able to correctly recognize the activities and verify the conformance of the process.

The other aspect evaluated is the processing time of the approach, to guarantee its applicability in a real setting. To evaluate the processing time, we computed the time used by the Complex Event Processing (CEP) to process events within a window and to notify the engine, plus the time for the engine to process the notification and possibly detect changes in the state of the model. For this assessment, we replayed all events in the test set as a continuous stream. Figure 1 shows the results of this assessment. In particular, VIOLA took on average 14 milliseconds to process the events in a window. Also, the processing time peaked at 23 milliseconds. We also noticed that the time to process a window was independent of the number of events previously processed. Similarly, we were unable to identify any correlation between the events being processed and the changes they caused in the state of the model.

References

1. Van Kasteren, T., Noulas, A., Englebienne, G., Kröse, B.: Accurate activity recognition in a home setting. In: Proc. of UbiComp. pp. 1–9 (2008)